

Application Of Data Analytics in Process Prediction, Analysis, Management & Visualization Using Microsoft Power Bi

Implementation of Power BI data analytics capabilities to monitor and optimize production in industries to minimize waste and energy loss while optimizing yield.

Chukwu, Christian Onyemaechi

Department of Chemical Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Owerri
PMB 1526 Imo State Nigeria

Chukwuchristian31@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1229-6956>

Web of Science: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/LPQ-6167-2024>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Christian-Chukwu>

Authorea: <https://www.authorea.com/users/851048-chukwu-christian-onyemaechi>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/chukwu-christian-onyemaechi/>

ABSTRACT

This project on the application of data analytics in process predictions, analysis, management, and visualisation using Microsoft Power BI is a research work aimed at developing an automated method to analyse and visualise the massive “big data” generated across chemical, process and manufacturing industries. To design an optimum means of converting production and sales data from industries into meaningful insights that can help Chemical Engineers, managers, technicians, and technologists optimise productions, save energy, and amass higher return on investment (ROI), this work tries to use Microsoft Power BI to predict, analyse, manage, and visualise data in process industries.

The research commenced with gathering production data collected in a polyvinyl chloride (PVC) products manufacturing company with advanced sensors installed at various data streams of the extrusion system. The acquired production data were duly cleaned, transformed, converted, processed, modelled, and visualised using Microsoft Power BI. Power BI is an advanced analytical tool that guarantees automated analysis of enormous amounts of data termed “big data”. Compared to the Microsoft Excel spreadsheet application, Power BI is popularly preferred due to its ability to process massive volumes of data in real-time at high speed and accuracy to provide valuable information for the company. Through proper extraction, transformation and loading of data into Power BI and subsequent analysis, this study discovered critical trends in the industry’s productivity by presenting the analysed data with the right visuals. The analysis and visualisation of the key variables in this study including process temperature, flow rate, torque, tool wear, energy consumption, and failure types show clear relationship and divergence. It was discovered that an unmonitored and insufficiently controlled PVC manufacturing system is susceptible to inconsistent production and generation of faulty outputs in the form of failed products. This anomaly consequently results to high energy consumption, tool wear, wastage, and costly production. For instance, at low and extremely high voltages, there were power failures and heat dissipation failures respectively. Therefore, to maintain a balance during the extrusion, the process conditions ought to be carefully monitored and properly adjusted over time.

Hence, the result of this study proves that the PVC production processes can be optimized by applying data analytics in predicting the activities within the extruder, analysing the manufacturing data, and visualising production conditions with Power BI to manage resources efficiently. If properly implemented by process industries, the findings of this research will help industries and production plants maximise the available limited resources, minimise waste, and generally increase productivity.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background Of This Study

The manufacturing industry today is dealing with various challenges. Uncertain shutdowns, increasing manufacturing costs, complexities in the supply chain, and machine operations and logistics are providing complications that must be addressed urgently. These challenges highlight the need for a solution to analyse the various types and large volumes of data that companies amass and visualize it in such a way that issues, trends, and opportunities can be readily identified.

The process of transforming data into insights for the purpose of improving business and operational decisions is referred to as big data analytics. Using this definition as a starting point, the community of chemical engineers had embarked on using data-driven modelling approaches many decades ago.

Some of the most foundational data-driven modelling work has been done in the chemical process industry, which has proven to be a fruitful ground for such work. Though not efficient in the chemical engineering context, the collection and storage of process data for the purpose of online monitoring and analysis were made possible by online instrumentation as well as centralized control systems. As a direct consequence of this, multivariate control, process monitoring, and inferential sensors have all enjoyed an exceptionally fast rate of adoption within the industry. Real-time model-based control, complex batch process monitoring, controller performance assessments, and integrated scheduling are some examples of new ways to use data that have more volume, variety, and speed because of recent advancements in computer hardware and numerical algorithms. These are all examples of new ways to use data. But despite the commendable improvements so far, chemical industries are still haunted by epileptic equipment breakdowns, faulty manufacturing, and high production costs.

The good news is business intelligence (BI) tools like Microsoft Power BI have the potential to solve many of these issues associated with the manufacturing sector. Power BI offers opportunities in multiple avenues to improve operations, including identifying top adopting trends and recognizing patterns for more accurate forecasting.

1.1.1 What Is Microsoft Power BI?

Power BI is a suite of business analytics and data visualization tools offered by Microsoft alongside Power Apps, Power Pages, Power Automate, and Power Virtual Agents collected in the Microsoft Power Platform suite. These desktop, cloud-based, self-service tools offer critical insights to business owners and engineers to assist them in making data-driven decisions. Power BI can enable companies, especially the chemical industries to seamlessly connect to and visualise any data using its unified, scalable platform for self-service and enterprise business intelligence (BI) which easily help decision-makers gain deeper data insights.

Businesses in the manufacturing industry can now leverage Power BI for sourcing, compiling, transforming, and modelling data from cloud-based or on-premises data warehouses originating from manufacturing, sales, and marketing data. When data is captured, they are easily processed, stored, managed, and visualised using Power BI, further empowering decision-makers with the right insights. The Power BI dashboard provides intuitive and interactive reports using the sourced data, making it easy to comprehend and share within and outside the organisation.

1.1.2 Digital Transformations in The Manufacturing Industry

The manufacturing industry today stands apart in its drive towards digital transformation using Power BI. Focused on reducing the cost of energy, optimising productivity, forecasting production, controlling processes, managing resources, and customising manufacturing solutions to meet the needs of consumers, chemical industries are now looking to IT solutions to alleviate its growing challenges. Modern data analysis technologies and strategies have created immense opportunities to move away from the traditional manual approach, such as Microsoft Excel and other manual data processing tools, and automate key processes to understand which KPIs (key performance indicators) are influencing business revenue and profit. Even beyond ascertaining the profitability of manufacturing, industries are more concerned about maximising production by reducing energy costs, minimising waste, and forecasting trends both in production and sales.

Smart meters, weather forecasts, and other data sources are improving the energy industry's forecasting capabilities, which allows for a better understanding of the energy consumption behaviours of large populations as well as the energy consumption behaviours of local neighbourhoods.

Electricity providers are also using these data sources to forecast demand surges, find faults and outages, and improve the reliability and efficiency of their systems.

In several previous trials, utilizing gathered information from automated systems helps the semiconductor industry bring down its overall cost of production. Applications of real-time automatic process control are making efforts to locate errors, increase yields, and lessen product variability.

Methods of machine learning, dimensionality reduction, and visualization are being incorporated into research and development in the pharmaceutical industry to facilitate the analysis of complex data sets such as gene expression, protein interactions, and drug discovery information. Additionally, model-based control, real-time optimization, and real-time process monitoring contribute to an improvement in quality within the pharmaceutical manufacturing industry.

The idea that the amount of data will continue to increase at an exponential rate is the defining characteristic of the era of big data. A speedy onslaught of information covering a diverse range of topics is expected.

Interestingly, digital transformation enabled by BI has resulted in improved efficiency, productivity, and profitability for manufacturing industries. By allowing innovation, it has also reduced the costs of data processing efforts by automating data capturing, analysis, and visualisation so that industrial leaders can focus on implementing the insights generated by Power BI. The clear impacts of Power BI on productivity have helped in the making of faster, data-driven decisions to better position companies to compete in today's fast-paced digital economy.

1.2 Problem Statement

The chemical industry, such as paint, plastics, pharmaceutical, metallurgy, cement, petrochemicals, and oil and gas sectors are continuously battling with numerous manufacturing setbacks, including pollution, uncertain machine shutdowns, increasing manufacturing costs, the inadequacy of raw materials, inflexible supply chains, and threatening climate change. These challenges are making the path harder for the manufacturing industries globally, reducing productivity across businesses and industries. Luckily, Power BI has the potential to solve many issues associated with manufacturing operations, from sourcing of raw materials and production of goods to marketing and sales by tracking production data, identifying KPIs and offering actionable insights to the company management, which empowers their decision-making. Power BI offers opportunities in multiple avenues to solve those

challenges faced in today's process industries by improving operations, including identifying the top adopting trends and recognizing patterns for more accurate forecasting.

1.3 Justification Of This Study

The impact of integrating Power BI in large-scale industrial data analytics and visualizations is immense. At a high level, Power BI can help you visualize your business data, monitor overall performance, and make well-informed business decisions with critical KPIs derived from multiple data sources. Power BI dashboards allow chemical engineering industries to generate report metrics such as trends per product, production volumes, and underperforming products. It can also integrate the visual metrics in Power BI with other solutions, such as ERP (enterprise resource planning) systems. A Power BI dashboard shows significant connectivity with third-party systems while forecasting important trends. On the finance side of the business, users can view information for a current financial situation within a specific date range through real-time financial reports.

CHAPTER 2

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. Materials

Data analysis and visualization in chemical and manufacturing industries has the capability to simplify complex facts and figures, transforming raw data into actionable business insights. The materials employed in this research project encompasses all the equipment utilized, both the physical and non-physical ones. Because it's a tech-based study, some of the tools used are non-material such as the major software and supporting application packages. The data sources and internet accesses required for the execution of this project are also non-tangible but remain core in the work. The primary physical and hardware materials used are the computers and their peripherals. Generally, the materials section will outline all the tools, equipment and facilities incorporated in this research which facilitated its completion and success. They are exhaustively discussed below:

1. Desktop computer, monitor and peripherals.
2. Laptop computer
3. Microsoft Power BI Desktop software
4. Data Source
5. Microsoft Office 365 applications
6. Microsoft Edge browser
7. Internet subscription

1.3.1 Desktop Computer, Monitor and Peripherals.

Desktop computer

Figure 1: HP Compaq Desktop Computer

The desktop computer employed in this project is HP Compaq Elite 8300 SFF Intel Core i5 3rd Gen 4GB RAM 500GB HDD Windows 11 Pro Desktop. It's a highly functional and super-fast computer running at 3.40GHz processor speed which facilitated faster processing of data. The efficient Intel HD Graphics 2500 card enabled a quicker rendering of visuals during the Power BI data visualization. The HP Compaq is a 64-bit operating system with x64-based processor which implied that all the complimentary software and application packages to run must be 64-bit compatible including the Power BI desktop. Coupled with the updated Windows 11 Pro 21H2 OS (operating system) build of 22000.2360 which is the most current pack as at the time of this report, the computer had high-performance and ability to multi-task especially when it was necessary to open multiple tabs or applications at once. The 500GB hard drive provided adequate storage while the 4GB RAM was enough to support faster data processing. There were also multiple USB, HDMI, and VGA ports to which other peripherals like monitor, keyboard, mouse, Bluetooth, and Wi-Fi were connected.

Monitor

Figure 2: NEC MultiSync Computer Monitor

The NEC MultiSync EA273W Mi system monitor was used as an output device in this project to provide wider view and ease of data and information visualization. It's a 27" extremely thin monitor with 1920 x 1080 resolution which align with its ultramodern design that enhances productivity during

this project. Ambient lights and human sensors enforce sustainable product concept while offering better ergonomics with 130 mm height adjustability. The ergonomic performance of the screen is further enhanced by the relatively large dot pitch for easy text readability and complements the excellent IPS image quality. The future-proof Display port, HDM, D-Sub and DVI-D.

1.3.2 Laptop Computer

Figure 3: HP Laptop 14-cf2xxx computer

As a backup tool for the research project especially for internet research and to gain condensed view of the Power BI visuals, a small-screen laptop computer HP 14-cf2xxx was used. Laptop HP 14-cf2xxx is a 14-inch screen size PC (personal computer) popular for its powerful Intel ® Core™ i3 10110U CPU running 2.10GHz clock speed. It has 4.0GB RAM (random access memory) and 1TB storage and powered by Windows 11 Pro Insider Preview (Evaluation copy, Build 23536 ni_prelease.230826-1546). Like the HP Compaq it was paired it with, this HP 14 is a 64-bit operating system with x64-based processor. It comes with high-resolution graphics drivers for better graphics rendering, and numerous ports for more connectivity.

1.3.3 Microsoft Power BI Desktop Software

Figure 4: Microsoft Power BI software

Power BI (Business Intelligence) is a Microsoft data modelling, analysis and visualization tool founded on the technological builds of Microsoft Excel spreadsheet, Structural Query Language (SQL) and PowerPoint applications. This is why users of Excel and PowerPoint find it more interesting as it combines the powerful and speedy calculations in Excel using (DAX-Data Analysis Expression) and PowerPoint extensive visualization capabilities. The Power Query, Power Pivot, and SQL components also give Power BI its reliable analytical and data processing power. At its highest level, Power BI enables organizations and companies to pull raw data from numerous sources whether offline, on a database or on cloud, and transform it into actionable insights that business owners, process engineers and project managers can implement, using a powerful, interactive, and easy-to-use user interface (UI). Generally, Power BI has a direct connectivity to various data sources and types (CSV, Excel, Database, SQL, Azure, social media, etc.), ability to compress data and extract only the necessary files and features, and varieties of visuals and report sharing features. Many users choose Power BI over other competitors like Tableau or Excel because it combines analytical, modelling and visualization capabilities found individually in others into one simple, powerful, and centralized dashboard (Model, Data and Report views). Microsoft Power BI come in Desktop, Mobile and cloud (Service) forms and can be downloaded through their website or on Microsoft Store.

1.3.4 Data Source

The data files used in this research were obtained on Kaggle (Kaggle, 2023). Kaggle is a world-renowned data sourcing community with millions of users globally. It collects, stores and shares dataset for data analysis, data science and machine learning projects freely. The data source I used in this research are credited to Lemuel Adams (2022) - plastic extrusion data, and Shivam (2021) - predictive maintenance data. Before being converted from CSV to Excel .xlsx, the PVC (polyvinyl chloride) extrusion and predictive maintenance data were 127 KB and 519 KB respectively.

1.3.5 Microsoft Office 365 Applications

Figure 5: Microsoft Office 365 Suite

Microsoft Office 365 is a premium corporate version of Microsoft office application packages. It's subscription-based (annual, monthly). Office 365 includes all the packages found in regular office be it 2021, 2019, 2016 or lower versions. The 365 copy of office have better features and capabilities that align with modern technological requirements in corporate and scientific settings. In this research, Microsoft Excel and Microsoft Word were used to review and inspect the data as well as compose this project report. Excel 365 provide the needed tool for the earlier analysis of the data before loading and transforming them with Power BI for further data modelling, analyst, and visualization. The Microsoft

Word application was used in writing, editing, and formatting the research report as well as for citing and referencing sources using an add-in called Mendeley cite. With Word 365, it is easier to share the report and collaborate with editors and project contributors.

1.3.6 Microsoft Edge Browser

Figure 6: Edge, Microsoft's official browser

Microsoft Edge is the official browser developed and used by Microsoft. Before now, Windows OS run on Internet Explorer browser until a few years ago when Microsoft released Edge and made it their standard browser across all their devices and OS especially windows 10 and 11. Aside from the Desktop version, there is a mobile and tablet versions of Microsoft Edge and all work seamlessly and can be synced across using Microsoft account. It's powerful, fast, and powered by AI (artificial intelligence).

1.3.7 Internet Subscription

To gain access to information online, there was a need for browsing data. Throughout this research, internet subscriptions were used to access data online, from preliminary internet research and gathering of literature to downloading of Power BI software and data source. I also used internet subscription to import other visuals that were not originally in Power BI desktop such as the Scroller visual as will be seen later.

1.4 Methodology

The methodology will introduce and elaborate on the processes and methods incorporated in this project, detailing all the steps employed in the researching, data analysis, and reporting which eventually produced the results obtained. In this project, both quantitative and qualitative methods (mixed) were applied in the sense that numerical data were used to derive actionable insights, with a qualitative analysis of the Power BI working principles. The data analyzed, modelled, and visualized were primary data sources obtained from Kaggle with a free license. The data sources were PVC pipes extrusion data set and predictive maintenance dataset respectively existing as CSV (comma-separated files) which were later inspected with Excel and converted to .xlsx (Excel workbook) format to avoid data loss and improve the table structure before loading into Power BI. Generally, this section will delve and explain all the steps followed to arrive to the final results of this research. All the steps will be extensively discussed especially as it pertains to the actual data analysis, modelling, and visualization using Power BI. Therefore, the methodology will commence with data inspection, transformation, modelling and proceed to analysis, visualization and finally reporting.

1.4.1 Data Inspection

Data analysis and visualization in Power BI often commence with a comprehensive study of the data source (file) even before defining the key objectives of the project. As part of the preliminary actions on the raw data, inspection play key role in ensuring the right type and form of data is used for the research. Therefore, data inspection is the meticulous survey and checks conducted on the data source to ascertain its veracity, size, authenticity, and usefulness to the project. During data inspection, the properties of the data such as number of columns, rows, file size, measured quantities, variables, etc. are checked thoroughly before loading into Power BI. Most Power BI data analysts often skip this first and important step hurriedly to save time. However, because the key objective of this research is understanding how Power BI can be effectively utilized in process prediction, analysis, visualization and management, every detail and steps were considered and executed irrespective of their minuteness.

Figure 7: Data Inspection of the two CSV data sources

To commence with the inspection process, the two data files (PVC extrusion dataset and predictive maintenance dataset) were opened with Microsoft Excel 365 desktop application. Afterwards, the csv file was “saved as” Excel workbook in a data conversion process. This conversion is a recommended standard because with the file existing in .xlsx format, it was easier to open, navigate and inspect the rows and columns. After the conversion, the file sizes for plastic extrusion and predictive maintenance increased from 127 KB and 519 KB to 179 KB and 565 KB respectively. The PVC extrusion file had 7 populated columns and 2 empty columns, and 5001 rows total while predictive maintenance file had 10 columns and 10001 rows. After the checks, it was confirmed that the data files contained the right columns and physical quantities required for a successful and accurate study of a typical PVC extrusion machine. They were therefore saved, and the spreadsheet closed.

1.4.2 Data Transformation

Figure 8: Data Loading and Transformation

The transformation of the raw data starts with opening the file into Microsoft Power BI after the previous inspection. Data transformation involves the processes of changing the data source from its initial state and form to the required condition essential for efficient analysis and visualization. Power BI desktop application was launched before opening the extrusion and predictive maintenance Excel data in the application. To grab and upload the data files, the “Get Data” button was used. Get Data is located in the Home tab and allows you to upload data into Power BI from numerous sources such as Excel Workbook, Power BI datasets, folders, Dataflows, website URL, SQL server, text/csv, SharePoint, azure, and many other channels.

In this project, the folder and Excel workbook options were used to introduce the data files. After bringing the data into Power BI, they’re neither yet saved nor loaded. At this stage, the files were reviewed for the last time to ensure they were the right files and data source for the project. After confirmation, they were either loaded or transformed. In my case, they were transformed prior to loading. Data transformation is recommended prior to loading because this enables the analyst to clean and shape the data before finally loading and saving them in Power BI.

The processes of data cleaning entails removing unnecessary columns, duplicate and empty cells, and data with errors. This goes along with shaping and profiling in which the tables were properly checked for quality. The data types (date, whole number, decimal number, text, etc.) of each column

were checked and corrected. It was also a stage in which the columns were renamed and formatted. The naming and renaming of columns during data transformation prior to data modelling and analysis is extremely important as it enhances efficiency and accuracy as well as ease of referring/calling tables while writing DAX (data analysis expression) codes.

During the data cleaning and shaping, it's very easy to retrace steps by using the “applied steps” feature. With the applied steps, some steps can be undone if there are noticed errors. It also enables faster editing of steps for example If a column or query were wrongly deleted or renamed. While a column can be renamed during data transformation, queries and tables can also be renamed or deleted in this stage. Also, during data transformation, columns are split, sorted, filtered, or grouped. The two datasets used in this project underwent these processes to eradicate the empty columns, duplicates, and tables with errors. After the data transformation, the datasets were then loaded into Power BI, the changes applied, and the project finally saved.

1.4.3 Data Modelling

Figure 9: Power BI Model View

The modelling of the two datasets began after the transformation. Now that the cleaning, shaping, and profiling processes confirmed the veracity of the dataset as well as improve its quality, they were then modelled in the model view. Data modelling is making the data in Power BI as accurate,

intentional, and purposeful as possible. During the data modelling, relationships were created across different fields and tables through merging and appending of related tables and data types. It provided an opportunity to expand the field size of the dataset. The initial fields were plastic extrusion and predictive but after the modelling through query merge, the data set was expanded to obtain PVCExtrusion, Process, Temperature, Failure and Product fields respectively (see the Power BI modelled star schema in the results chapter)

PVCExtrusion here is the FACT table while Process, Temperature, Failure and Product fields represented the DIM (dimension) tables. During this project, it was unavoidable to break the dataset down into tables for better analysis and visualization. The FACT table is usually one and often keeps data that might be aggregated in the reporting visualization. In contrast, the DIM tables can be as many as possible. DIM tables store descriptive information that can slice and dice the data in the FACT table. The FACT tables usually contain key data that is compared against supporting data located in the DIM tables. The combination of the FACT and DIM tables forms a relationship. In my case, star schema relationship was formed by placing the PVCExtrusion field (FACT table) at the centre of the DIM tables (Process, Temperature, Failure and Product fields).

Figure 10: Star Schema of the Data Model

The essence of the DIM tables was to group similar and related columns into one or more tables using common keys. This process was possible using the merge feature. During column or table merge, one could merge two or more queries as new and different queries with a new name or simply merged into any of the existing ones without creating a new query. However, for merging to be possible, a common key was created in both the plastic extrusion data set and predictive maintenance dataset. In power BI analysis and visualization, it's a tradition that both tables ready for merge must have common

keys. Specifically, the target columns must have the same data types even if not same column titles. For example, a column with texts cannot be merged with another that contained whole numbers.

Figure 11: Merging Queries in Power BI using Key Columns

Merging works perfectly when there are same or very similar data or columns on one or more tables. Reiteratively, a key field is an important field that makes the data to be merged identical (it often appears as an ID or index numbers). Therefore, when a DIM table don't have a key field, add one by going to the Add Colum tab then add an index column counting from 1. Summarily, one of the golden rules of data modelling in Power BI observed during this stage of the project was not to have FACT and descriptive columns in the same field or table. Thus, by breaking and separating the tables into FACT and DIM, the performance of the dataset was optimized.

1.4.4 DAX – Data Analysis Expression

Data Analysis Expression (DAX) is an effective mathematical and analytical tool that provided the needed tool for statistical analysis and addition of more tables and columns. is an elegant and easy to learn formula language used in Power BI, Power Pivot and SSAS Tabular to add analytical value to your data model. DAX improves data models by allowing users to extract more value from their data and make more informed business decisions. Microsoft specifically developed DAX to support a large

user base. DAX is much easier to learn than traditional technical languages, making it an ideal language for users who don't come from a technical background but want to do their own Self-service Business Intelligence. DAX is often compared to an advanced version of Excel, having high-end capability of managing and manipulating data. Many DAX functions are similar to Excel functions, which means new Power BI users can leverage their existing Excel knowledge to make an easy transition to writing and authoring DAX formulas. While there are similarities between DAX and Excel, the two languages are not interchangeable.

DAX is a functional language, which means formulas are constructed by applying and composing various functions. The functions can contain other nested functions, conditional statements, and value references. Execution starts from the innermost function, or parameter, and works outward, making formatting important. DAX works with data that is stored in a tabular data model. These models are comprised of one or more tables, each table containing columns and rows of data. There are two primary data types: Numeric and non-numeric or other. Numeric includes integers, decimals, dates, and currency, while other includes strings and binary objects. If a function works on a number, it works for any numeric data type. While you can create Power BI reports that show valuable insights without using DAX formulas, creating effective DAX formulas will help you get the most out of your data, providing insight and solutions that might be missed with typical analysis.

Calculated Columns and Calculated Measures

Calculated columns are primarily used to add new columns to a table providing more ways to describe and break down the data. For example, you may add an age column to a customer table so that sales and profit margin can be analyzed and broken down by age demographic. Another common use case for creating calculated columns is to create a unique key on a table, which may be necessary to define a relationship between two tables. In this research, calculated columns were used to expand the measures, variables and quantity and quality of the dataset by creating new columns to better understand the data. Some of the added columns were indexes and key columns throughout PVCExtrusion, Product, Temperature and Process tables. Two extra and very important DAX calculated columns were added to the Failure table namely Alarm, Comments, and Action. These DAX powered columns are intended to provide more clarity to the dataset and enable process controllers in monitoring the production, receive feedback quickly and know the right actions to take.

Calculated Measures are dynamic calculations that recalculate depending on how a report is viewed or filtered. For example, if a user changed a time-range slider on a report, the measures on that

report would be recalculated to reflect the time-range selected. Unlike calculated columns which are calculated during processing of the data model, measures are calculated at runtime when a report is opened or when a user interacts with the filters on a report. Therefore, the results of a measure are always changing and are not stored in your database. Calculated measures are different from columns in quite a few ways as shown in this table.

Table 1: Differences Between Calculated Columns and Calculated Measures

Calculated Columns	Calculated Measures
<i>The results of calculated columns are immediately viewable in the table.</i>	The results of calculated measures are not stored in the table.
<i>Calculated columns can be used in filters and slicers.</i>	Calculated measures cannot be used in filters and slicers.
<i>Calculated columns are updated when the data model is refreshed.</i>	Calculated measures are dynamic and calculated as filters are applied.
<i>Calculated columns take up more space in the data model.</i>	Calculated measures do not take up space in the model.
<i>Calculated columns are not dynamic.</i>	Calculated measures are dynamic and always changing based on the filters applied.

Common DAX Functions

Table 2: DAX Functions and their Examples

<i>MATH & STATS Functions</i>	<i>LOGICAL Functions</i>	<i>TEXT Functions</i>	<i>FILTER Functions</i>	<i>DATE & TIME Functions</i>
Basic aggregation functions as well as “iterators” evaluated at the row-level	Functions for returning information about values in a given conditional expression	Functions to manipulate text strings or control formats for dates, times, or numbers	Lookup functions based on related tables and filtering functions for dynamic calculations	Basic date and time functions as well as advanced time intelligence operations
<i>Common Examples:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SUM • AVERAGE • MAX/MIN • DIVIDE • COUNT/COUNTA • COUNTROWS • DISTINCTCOUNT 	<i>Common Examples:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IF • IFERROR • AND • OR • NOT • SWITCH • TRUE • FALSE 	<i>Common Examples:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CONCATENATE • FORMAT • LEFT/MID/RIGHT • UPPER/LOWER • PROPER • LEN • SEARCH/FIND • REPLACE • REPT • SUBSTITUTE • TRIM • UNICHAR 	<i>Common Examples:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CALCULATE • FILTER • ALL • ALLEXCEPT • RELATED • RELATEDTABLE • DISTINCT • VALUES • EARLIER/EARLIEST • HASONESVALUE • HASONEFILTER • ISFILTERED • USERRELATIONSHIP 	<i>Common Examples:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DATEDIFF • YEARFRAC • YEAR/MONTH/DAY • • HOUR/MINUTE/SECOND • TODAY/NOW • WEEKDAY/WEEKNUM

- Iterator Functions:*
- *SUMX*
 - *AVERAGEX*
 - *MAXX/MINX*
 - *RANKX*
 - *COUNTX*

- Time Intelligence Functions:*
- *DATESYTD*
 - *DATESQTD*
 - *DATESMTD*
 - *DATEADD*
 - *DATESINPERIOD*

1.4.5 Data Visualization

Figure 12: Advanced Home View of the Report View

The data visualization capability of Microsoft Power BI is a core and outstanding lure for most data analysts. It's the first feature that anyone would easily and quickly identify. Power BI has numerous kinds and forms of visuals for presenting data. When a data is properly visualized, decision makers and the audience can then easily understand the key outcomes of the data analysis and be able to make data-backed decision. Since this project centered on the application of data analytics in process predictions, analysis, management, and visualization using Microsoft Power BI, a favourable attention was allotted to the report view page. The right visuals such as line and stacked column chart, pie chart, line chart, scroller, clustered column chart, card visuals and slicers were maximized in effectively visualizing the data.

Some of the key focus areas in analyses and visualizing the data was to understand the relationships between all the variables especially the impacts of other physical conditions such as process temperature, rotational speed, screw speed, flow rate and even metering length on the failure type of the PVC materials and their energy consumption. Therefore, the right visuals were appropriately inserted to match the different measures. In the report view, there are eight pages of

reports with each one focusing on a particular process condition and their impacts on the materials failure. As a matter of fact, with the right visuals, identifying the causes of the failure of the PVCs during the extrusion process was straightforward.

To create any report, various visuals are selected from the visuals pane and data dragged from the data pane into the canvasses. Depending on the kind of visual selected, there are options to add aggregations, filter the visuals and format the columns and rows or the entire visualization. Power BI further offers the ability to switch between visuals at any stage of the visualization. The formatting feature facilitates the editing of visual size and style, title, callout values, category labels and cards. There is also a very helpful visual in the insert menu called Q&A that create an interactive atmosphere between the report user/viewer and power BI. With Q&A, anyone can ask questions regarding the entire data and receive detailed responses. This feature is essential especially to a novice or an audience who want to extract quick information from the visualization.

Similarly, another important visual that that boosts the efficiency of Power BI reports is the slicers. Slicers facilitates a fast and efficient sorting and filtering of data by slicing through the visuals. When slicers are inserted and a particular data, variable, table, or measure is selected in the slicer, the entire report view are filtered to show only the information for the selected value. This is an essentially useful capability that enhances user accessibility to the results of the data analysis and visualization without sieving through the entire voluminous information.

1.4.6 Reporting, Insights Communication and Decision Making (Process Control)

Figure 13: Publishing and Sharing of Power BI Reports

The last step in every Power BI project is always reporting and communicating the analysis and visualization findings to an audience. In business settings, Power BI developers and analysts communicate their findings to managers and directors who in turn translate them into decisions. Thus, the essence of any Power BI project is to help organization, companies, and industries to understand their data and use the findings to influence decision making. Without properly sharing the outcome of the project, the entire lifecycle of the analysis and visualization becomes futile. Visualizations, Q&A, publishing and sharing of the published report demonstrates a successfully completed BI project.

As process engineers, understanding the results of Power BI project is critical in taking core decisions. In this research, emphasis was placed on adopting the appropriate visualization engineers can easily understand and implement. Instead of just one page of report, 8 pages were built to detail each process measure and their contributions to the failure of the PVC pipes during extrusion. The pages are process summary, temperature, flow rate, torque, tool wear, energy consumption, PVC failure, process control. They are elaborated discussed in the results and discussion section of this report.

After completing a Power BI project, it's either published to the Power BI service, saved as Power BI project file, or converted into PDF (portable document format) for sharing. The essence of publishing and sharing of BI reports is to reach more audiences who need the results to understand the production process. In my case, the reports were published, converted, and shared with the chief manager, directors, production engineers and other process control technicians. Afterwards, the concerned persons utilized the report in adjusting the process conditions as required in order to optimize productions, minimize waste of the PVC raw materials, and save energy expended in the manufacturing of faulty/failed products.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

The result of this project cut across the data model, DAX calculations, and visualizations. These three components make up the findings of this project and each one is distinct in both methodology and impacts. They will be individually evaluated sequentially according to their order of execution during the actual data analysis and visualization in Power BI. The results of this project are extensive and inexhaustive, but the key findings shall be incorporated and highlighted to provide a comprehensive report to the audience and a potential user of this work.

4.1.1 Model building

Modeling in Power BI is a process of creating relationships between tables, queries, and fields to indicate connection and enhance further analysis and visualization. To create a clearer model structure, this project adopted the star schema approach in which the FACT table is centralized and surrounded by the descriptive tables as seen below:

Figure 14: The Modelled PVC Extrusion and Predictive Maintenance Datasets

The PVCExtrusion field contains the FACT tables. These are numerical and primary data which contains key information required for an effective study of the PVC extrusion process. Some of the important tables contained therein include the material flow rate (kg/h), tool wear (m), torque (Nm), rotational speed (rpm), energy conversion (kJ/kg), failure type and product type. These are the fundamental measures of this research which are complimented by the DIM field values (air, process and barrel temperatures, product ID). As cited earlier in the methodology, the FACT and DIM tables serve varying purposes often during the visualization. Aside from improved dataset quality, breaking down the tables enhances data categorization and grouping.

During the visualization in the report view of Microsoft Power BI, the tables and variables in the FACT table are compared against those in DIM tables. For instance, in the Temperature page of the Power BI report, failure types (No failure, overstrain failure, power failure, etc.) were compared alongside the process temperature to understand how the temperature gradient of the extruder influences the type of failure obtained at each temperature increase or decrease.

4.1.2 DAX Analysis

All the DAX calculations were performed within Data View of Power BI. The Data View section of Power BI dashboard is where major data analysis expressions and computations are made. It offers an ability to directly add new columns and tables. More importantly, DAX expressions (codes or programs) can be written here to calculate new columns and tables. Recall that DAX is to Power BI what MATLAB language is to the MATLAB application. DAX expressions make use of functions, operators, and constants to perform pure mathematical calculations and statistical analysis in a speed of light. During this project, more columns were added to various tables to expand the data set and build new measures essential in subsequent analysis and visualizations as shown below:

Comments =

```
IF(Failure[Failure Type]="No Failure", "Everything is perfect",  
IF(Failure[Failure Type]="Power Failure", "The power is down",  
IF(Failure[Failure Type]="Overstrain Failure", "Material under intense strain",  
IF(Failure[Failure Type]="Tool Wear Failure", "Equipment wearing out",  
IF(Failure[Failure Type]="Heat Dissipation Failure", "Heat supply is excessive",  
"System automatically adjusting"))))
```


by an automated error tracer and corrector which is expected to fix the problem. If the system functions perfectly, an alarm technology powered by sensors is expected to notify control engineers who activate the actuators that immediately locates the problem in the system and fixes it. For an AI (artificial intelligence) powered PVC extruder (as I propose), when an alarm sounds, the AI detects the source of the error and inform the controller. The controller then activates an error correction system that adjust the process conditions whether it's temperature, flow rate, rotational speed, or screw speed.

4.1.3 Data Visualization

Data visualization was the last stage of this Power BI project. With several visuals available, the first task of this stage was choosing the most appropriate visual for each field or visualization. A line graph is best suited for data values that shows gradients. Bar charts and clustered columns are alike. Pie chart also is recommended for tables that illustrate percentage increase. To get started with the visualization, charts are picked from the visual's column. You can simply click on it or drag and drop into the canvas. Proceed to drag the appropriate data from the data page. You may also add more data into the various axes and slicers. Afterwards, proceed to adding card visuals and specialized slicers that will enable you sort the visuals.

Below are the 8 report pages of this research with each page accounting for single measure, often compared to the failure type of the extrusion process. Further explanations on the relationships between the variables in each visualization is discussed in the discussion section.

Figure 16: Process Summary Visualisation

Figure 17: Temperature Visualisation

Figure 18: Flow Rate Visualisation

Figure 19: Torque Visualisation

Figure 20: Tool Wear Visualisation

Figure 21: Energy Consumption Visualisation

Figure 22: PVC Failure Visualisation

Figure 23: Process Control Visualisation

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1 Modelling

This section will elaborate on the findings of the results in details, add more clarity to the points established in methodology. The analysis, modelling and visualization of the raw extrusion and productive maintenance data produced three basic results: data model, calculated columns, and eight visualizations. The data model is a star schema showing active and inactive relationships between PVCExtrusion and Process, Temperature, Product and Failure tables. Each are connected by unique values. There's a one-to-one (1:1) relationship existing between PVCExtrusion (FACT table) and Process table using the ProcessKey created in the Process table to match an existing key column the PVCExtrusion table. Similarly, there are other one-to-one relationships between PVCExtrusion table and Temperature, Failure and Product tables respectively linked y unique identities which varies across the fields.

4.2.2 DAX

In the Data View, the DAX calculations were used to create new columns (alarm, comments, and action). With the help of DAX expression, lines of codes were written in a matter of few minutes in the DAX editor. Using the Comments column as an example, the expression writing began with naming the table (Comments) followed by equality sign and the main statistical expression that computed and populated the DAX column. Because it's a conditional column, conditional statement was used (IF). In the second line of the expression, *IF (Failure [Failure Type] = "No Failure", "Everything is perfect"*, Power BI DAX goes to the *Failure* table/query to find the *Failure Type* column and locate the cells containing *No Failure*. It then returns and saves the answer before proceeding to the next line. On the 7th line where the expression was closed with five brackets, DAX finally returns the complete answers for all the lines and then populate the Comments column with the right responses. In a case whereby there is an error in the DAX expression, the table is either filled with the *#ERROR* or no computation is done at all. However, Power BI error detection system will always return error messages and potential solutions. Notably, while writing DAX codes, IntelliSense, Power BI's resourceful suggestion system often guides one with suggestions and options to choose while typing.

Generally, DAX expressions are very handy but note that while the calculated columns add the new columns to the table, calculated measures don't. instead, all calculated measures are viewable only in the report view and can be used in the visualization even though they won't be stored in the

project. If there are columns and tables are not needed in the report and visualization, they are switched off or hidden. This is recommended especially if there are numerous datasets or unrequired data created earlier. The hidden tables and queries won't be loaded into the data model and visualization.

4.2.3 Visualization

The visualizations in the report view shows all the eight pages sequentially arranged. Each page presents unique measures, have different objectives, and serve varying purpose. They are individually discussed below:

1. Process Summary

The process summary page shows a comprehensive and condensed description of the entire extrusion visualization in one view. Here, the failure types (no failure, power failure, overstrain failure, tool wear failure, heat dissipation failure, and random failure) is plotted against the various PVC products. The values on y-axis represent the average number of products that failed while the x-axis has all the failure types. Note that all the products had failure values, but not all really failed. The “no failure” products are the only good ones that were extruded successfully. The remaining plastics had one fault, or another caused by either power failure, overstrain, tool wear, heat dissipation and random failures. The third line y-axis contains rotational speed (rpm) table values. From the visual, it's noticeable that about 3,915 products did not fail which accounted for the majority of the products. Considering the lengths of the individual failure type columns, “no failure” is the tallest indicating that a huge number of the products were not faulty.

There are 44 products that failed due to power issue, 34 failed due to overstrain, 15 failed due to tool wear, 7 failed due to heat dissipation and only seven products failed due to random factors. The card visuals by the right of the visualization summarizes key points of this page: there are 4022 total number of products, 309.08 K average temperature, 1540 rpm rotational speed and about 1,000,000 kJ/kg of energy consumed in the production most of which count as waste due to the failures. The slice by the right near the Q&A is used in filtering the entire visualization according to the product type. The Q&A card provides the needed support and assistance for asking questions directly on the visualizations and getting feedback. By simply typing in questions or selecting from the existing likely questions and FAQs (frequently asked question), you can get instant answers and summaries about the data.

2. Temperature

The temperature report page places the average process temperature side by side with the failure type in the first left-ward visualization. It also compares the failure type with the sum of process temperature. Above the visualization, the individual cards shows that the average process temperature of the extruder is 309.08 K, average air temperature is 299.14 K with the barrel temperatures reading 2615, 237 and 235 Celsius maximum temperatures respectively. Across the extruder barrels, from barrel 1 to barrel 2 and 3, there is a noticed temperature drop. This is expected because throughout the extrusion process, temperature gradient decreases along the extrusion line.

In the first temperature visualization, heat dissipation accounted for 310.70 K average temperature which is no surprise. This is followed by random failure and tool wear failure types. Coming fourth is No Failure while overstrain failure and power failure comes later. From this visualization, it's empirically obvious that at high temperature, heat dissipation caused lots of failures. Also, when the power supply was very low, there was power failure. Therefore, to manufacture PVC products with no failure, an average temperature of 309.08 K should be maintained and regulated. Any temperature over or below this threshold would result to product failure.

3. Flow Rate

Flow rate measures the amount of plastic materials flowing through the extruder per unit time (kg/h). A line graph was used to compare the increase and decrease of material failure with the flow rate throughout the production. From the visualization, an increase in flow rate resulted to higher number of failures. This could be due to a malfunctioning extruder component. Nevertheless, this anomaly accounts for the importance of flow rate in the production of PVC products. PVCs are plastic materials made from polyvinyl pellets which are plastic polymers. A variation in the heat supply and temperature of the extruder, surrounding air and barrels obviously affect the flowability of the semi-solid materials flowing through the extruder. When not checked, a suddenly increased flow rate extrudes many failed products.

In this ideal extrusion system, the recommended average flow rate is 52.25 kg/h. At any flow rate slightly above or below this value could result to errors and failures which ultimately increase waste and production cost.

4. Torque

The torque (Nm) measured throughout the production process indicates that the higher the torque, the more failed PVC products are extruded. At a torque of 60 Nm, there were too many overstrain

failures. The values decrease from heat dissipation failure, power failure, no failure and random failure down to tool wear failure where there was less torque and tool wear. This analysis indicates that an increased torque generated more faulty products and causes disastrous tool wear.

From the card visuals, an average torque of 39.97 Nm will be sufficient to yield products with no failure. At a minimum torque of 3.80 Nm and maximum torque of 76.20 Nm, there are bound to be faulty extrudates resulting in overstrain failure or tool wear failure. The slicer at the extreme upper right corner can be used to gauge the torque values and failure types by sliding it left or right.

5. Tool wear

Tool wear (m) is a measure of the amount of worn out in an equipment often caused by friction or agedness of the tools. Equipment wear in a PVC extrusion line can result to underperformance of the extruder and other components. In the tool wear visualization, the tool wear failure (214.67 m) was rampant with an increase in the average tool wear. It afterwards decreased down to heat dissipation at 88.57 m average tool wear. As can be seen on the visualization, the total tool wear is 437,000 m, 108.53 m average, and 246 m maximum tool wear. Generally, about 239 instances of tool wear were recorded during the production. On the tool wear report page is also a tool called smart narratives.

Smart narrative is an AI feature in Power BI that automatically summarizes the visualization in a page into texts, highlighting key metrics and trends. From the smart narrative analysis, at 214.67, Tool Wear Failure had the highest Average of Tool Wear (m) and 142.37% higher than Heat Dissipation Failure which had the lowest average tool wear of 88.57%. These insights from smart narratives confirms the values plotted on the chart. Smart narratives are very effective especially for complicated graphs and charts. When enabled, it scans through the plotting and extract concise summaries of the data.

6. Energy Consumption

Energy consumption is a major consideration in chemical engineering industries and PVC manufacturing companies aren't left out. With a rising cost in energy globally, every process industry today should pay attention to their energy consumption both the amount effectively utilized for useful production and the wastes. In the extrusion dataset used in this research, voluminous amount of energy was wasted due to the multiple failures. This energy consumption varies across product types and failure types.

From the energy consumption visualization, the product type was compared with the volume of energy consumption per product type. The L-type consumed 60.12% of the energy; H-type, 10.12%;

and M-type, 29.76%. The total energy utilized in the manufacturing was 1,000,000 kJ/kg with a minimum consumption of 258 kJ/kg and maximum of 419 kJ/kg. Summarily, L had the sum of energy consumption at 792313 kJ/kg, followed by product type M at 397112 kJ/kg and H at 134322 kJ/kg.

7. PVC Failure

Detecting the failure of the PVC products during extrusion has been part of the key objectives of this research. If failures could be predicted and identified before they occur through the analysis and visualization of the extrusion process, process engineers would have more leverage to manage the manufacturing process. In the failure page of the Power BI report, the number of products reading 'no failure' were highest compared to those that malfunctioned due to power failure and other failures. As shown on the visualization, approximately 3,915 PVC products were successfully extruded without any impairment. The remaining products were faulty due to several factors such as low or high temperature, flow rate, power supply, rotational speed, etc.

Generally, this extrusion not only produced faulty finished materials, but also consumed large volume of energy (1M kJ/kg) at high production and maintenance cost.

8. Process Control

The process control report page provides effective system control mechanism that the control technologists can use to monitor the process and handle faults and breakdowns. A multi-row card was used to visualize the different fault types of failures, and their alarm, comments, and action. When the production is running smoothly the automated process monitoring system reports that everything is perfect, and no further action is required. But in cases whereby there us heat dissipation failure or other failure types, the system reports on the problem and takes action immediately to correct the problem. Fixing the faults in the extrusion process might involve altering the production conditions and variables such as air temperature, process temperature, flow rate, rotational speed, screw speed or the temperatures of the three barrels. In an ideal PVC plant as I envision, an automated error corrector will be responsible for quickly troubleshooting and solving the issues to avoid further loss to the industry in forms of tool wear, energy waste or multiple failures.

CHAPTER 4

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research project has duly studied the failure of PVC products in an extrusion process with key interest on how other internal and external conditions in the extruder such as process and air temperatures, flow rate, rotational speed, tool wear and torque affect production and influence rate of failure and energy consumption. The research commenced with the specification of project objectives, data collection, inspection, modelling, analysis, visualization, and reporting using Power BI. Microsoft Power BI is an effective tool for deriving insights from structured and unstructured data. Through a clear methodology, I performed an in-depth analysis and visualization to generate the results discussed in the results section.

Generally, my discovery in this research indicates that an uncontrolled PVC manufacturing system is bound to generate inconsistent yields in the form of failure and can consume more energy than supposed due to all the wasteful work done in extruding faulty products. Therefore, my research proposes that the PVC production process can be optimized by applying data analytics in process predictions, analysis, management, and visualization using Microsoft Power BI. This has been exhaustively demonstrated in this work, but future research is encouraged to explore several discrepancies and discover how best to deploy Power BI in process control effectively.

In the meantime, the following were threatening challenges to this project which inhibited both progress and success. On a personal level, they include unavailability of free data source online especially ones from manufacturing companies. Also, this type of research is time intensive and requires adequate timeframe of consistent research. Though IT-based research, this study was averagely costly and therefore requires enough financial backing in procuring the perfect computer, subscribing to Power BI pro and regular internet subscription. More importantly, the field of data analytics using Microsoft Power BI in the chemical industries is yet to be explored. Thus, literature was scanty, making the literature review to rely heavily on general data analytics, data science and machine learning resources. On the industrial scale, the challenges to the application of Power BI in process industries includes the unavailability of advanced sensors to collect manufacturing data and inadequacy of the technological and technical know-how who can capture the massive and often wasted big data and transform them into useful decision-making tool as I did in this project.

To alleviate and eradicate the shortcomings mentioned above, I therefore recommend the following:

1. Manufacturing industries should make their production data available online for public use. This will cut down the search time spent in scavenging for the right dataset.
2. Universities should be able to sponsor students with financial assistances in future research of this nature. This will help cut cost so that the student can focus on carrying out successful research.
3. Educational institutions and stakeholders in the education system are encouraged to empower young people with Power BI data analysis, visualization, and reporting skills through free live and online trainings.
4. Chemical industries should begin to maximize their massive production data to generate useful insights. This can only be performed by experienced data analysts who should be properly remunerated and encouraged to deliver efficient results.
5. Lastly, local industries are encouraged to collaborate to develop analytical capabilities to start exploiting their data locally instead of depending on foreign partners.

Generally, the future of Power BI data analysis' role in chemical engineering is bright and promising if the recommendations above are implemented to the last. Nevertheless, the community of chemical engineers still has work to do to overcome upcoming technical, platform, and cultural challenges. Academic institutions, private businesses, and public agencies need to work together on workforce development and analytics innovation if they want to take advantage of the opportunities. The early adopters of big data technologies are responsible for motivating the rest of the community to embark on the big data journey and establishing a culture that emphasizes the ongoing pursuit of new opportunities. Power BI hold potentials for the chemical and allied industries. Therefore, to accelerate this journey of fully maximising the "big data", especially in process industries, stakeholders are encouraged to adopt Power BI to predict, analyse, visualise, and manage production process optimally, thereby maximising energy and saving cost.

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